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EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HUMIC ACIDS FROM SOME BROWN AND HARD COALS OF TAJIKISTAN**OLIFTAEVA ZHOLA ABDULNIYOZOVNA**

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Abstract: The study of humic acids (HA) is associated with their rich composition, complex structure, and high biological activity. The objects of this research were industrially developed deposits of hard and brown coals, including Shurob, Fon-Yagnob, Ziddi, Sayod, Nazar-Ayloq, and Kurtegin. The work focuses on the extraction of humic acids, determination of ash-forming elements, and investigation of the structural and functional-group composition of the isolated products.

Keywords: coals, humic acids extraction, structure, macro- and microelements, pyrophosphate.

Humic acids constitute the major fraction of humic substances widely distributed in nature, occurring in soils, peat, lignite (brown coal), and higher plants. In microphases, they are also present in certain food products such as roasted coffee, black tea, the crust of black bread, mumiyo (shilajit), and roasted meat. The scientific application of humic acid preparations in medicine and veterinary practice began in 1967. Owing to their astringent, antiresorptive, and antiviral properties, humic acid preparations are particularly effective in the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases and metabolic disorders regulated by intestinal immunity.

The hypothetical structure (Fig. 1) of a fragment of soil humic acids demonstrates that humic substances represent a complex mixture of macromolecules with variable composition and irregular structure. Classical laws of thermodynamics and traditional concepts of molecular structure are not directly applicable to such systems. The fundamental properties of humic substances include non-stoichiometric composition, structural irregularity, heterogeneity of structural elements, and polydispersity. When dealing with humic substances, the concept of a single, well-defined molecule disappears; instead, they should be considered as molecular ensembles. Consequently, conventional quantitative approaches used to describe organic compounds—such as determining the exact number of atoms in a molecule and the types of chemical bonds—cannot be applied. In this sense, humic substances may be regarded as a “black box” in which processes occur unpredictably and differently each time.

Fig. 1

Materials and Methods:

The aim of the present work was to isolate humic acids from brown and hard coals of the selected deposits, to determine the ash-forming elements in coal-derived humic acids, and to study their structural and functional-group composition. At the initial stage, the moisture content, ash

content, and bitumen fraction of the coal samples were determined. Subsequently, humic acids were extracted.

Analysis of the ash composition of the investigated coal samples revealed the presence of 21 macro- and microelements, including Ti, Ni, B, Mo, Zn, Co, Na, Ca, Al, Mn, Sn, Mg, Fe, Pb, Si, Cr, Cu, V, P, and Ag. Their contents varied from 0.00086% (Pb) to 27.10% (Si). During alkaline extraction of humic acids from coal, a portion of these elements passed into the extract in bound form.

Humic acids were isolated from coal samples by water and alkaline extraction followed by precipitation in an acidic medium, as well as by a modified dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) method. The yield of humic acids from the investigated coal samples ranged from 9% to 23% (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Content of Exipipients and Humic Acids in Samples of the Called Fields of Coals

Names fields coal		Contents,%					
		Humidity	Ash-content	Bitumens	*exit of humic acids	**exit of humic acids	Ash-content of humic acids
1	Shurob	7,2-11,59	10,01-13,36	11,1-14,70	22,66		2,43-5,94
2	Fon-Jagnob	19,8	2,28	18,18	15,4	19,90	0,8
3	Ziddi	5-19,92	2,18-8,96	7,14	16,5		4,37
4	Nazar-Ayloq	2,65	2,6-3,55	2,04-5,54	9,54		0,26
5	Sayod	6,92	16,4-32,11	15,21	16,6	17,50	0,04
6	Kurtekin	2,2-9,83	3,0-4,5	3,0-3,62	13,19		0,25

Spectroscopic studies using ^{13}C NMR and IR spectroscopy confirmed the polyfunctional nature of the isolated humic acids. Thermochemical (TGA/DSC) studies indicated the presence of complementary interactions between high-molecular and low-molecular fractions, forming an irregular structure that gradually transforms from a loose to a more condensed form.

Results and Discussion

Tajikistan possesses several large brown coal deposits, among which the widely exploited Shurob deposit occupies a significant place. Humic acids were extracted from brown coal of this deposit. The first stage of the study involved determination of the moisture content of coal by drying at 100–120 °C in a drying oven. The moisture content was found to be 11.59% of the total coal mass. The Hoffman method was also applied, involving drying over P_2O_5 to constant weight, yielding a moisture content of 11.82%.

To remove bitumen compounds, coal samples were treated with toluene, resulting in the extraction of bitumen-like substances amounting to 11.1% of the initial coal mass. Ash content was determined by complete combustion of the coal sample in air followed by weighing of the non-combustible residue, which amounted to 15.36%.

The total yield of humic acids was determined using the pyrophosphate method ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$), which involves treatment of the coal sample with an alkaline sodium pyrophosphate solution, followed by extraction with sodium hydroxide, precipitation of humic acids with excess hydrochloric acid, and gravimetric determination of the precipitate.

$$m_x = \frac{100 \cdot V \cdot (m_1 - m_2)}{V_1 \cdot m} \quad (1)$$

where m_1 is the mass of dry humic acids, g

m_2 – mass of humic acid ash, g,

V_1 – total volume of an aliquot of an alkaline solution taken for precipitation denition of humic acids, cm^3

To determine the total ash, we used the method of determining the weight of the non-combustible residue after complete combustion in air and weighing the residue after firing, which

amounted to 15.36%. To determine the total yield of humic acids, we used the pyrophosphate method ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$), the essence of which is the treatment of an analytical sample of coal with an alkaline solution of sodium hydroxide, precipitation of humic acids with an excess of hydrochloric acid and determination of the mass of humic acids with an excess of hydrochloric acid and determination of the mass of the resulting sediment

$$m_x = \frac{100 \cdot V \cdot (m_1 - m_2)}{V_1 \cdot m} \quad (1)$$

where m_1 is the mass of dry humic acids, g,

m_2 – mass of humic acid ash, g,

V – total volume of alkaline solution, cm³

V_1 – total volume of alkaline solution, cm³

V_1 – total volume of an aliquot of an alkaline solution taken for precipitation denition of humic acids, cm³,

The mass of a sample of coal calculated as coal in a dry, ash-free state, g, calculated by the formula:

$$m_y = m_3 \frac{100 - (W^a + A^a)}{100}, \text{ где } (2)$$

m_3 – mass of coal sample, g,

W^a - mass fraction of analytical moisture in coal, % A^a - ash content of analytical coal sample, %.

A^a - ash content of analytical coal sample, %.

The isolated humic acids were obtained as a dark brown amorphous mass without a clearly defined melting point. Table 1 summarizes the analytical results and demonstrates the reproducibility and accuracy of the applied methods.

The isolated humic acids are a dark brown mass that does not have a clear melting point. Table 1 shows the accuracy of the method and the results obtained

The total mass fraction of humic acids and the yield of free humic acids in terms of dry ash-free or dry ash-free and bitumen-free state as a percentage were calculated using the formula:

Table 1

Accuracy of the method

Coal weight (G)	Coal moisture content, %	Presence of bitumen in coal, %	Mass of coal ash, %	Yield of humic acids, %	Masses of ash HA, %
2	11,59	11,1	15,36	20,34	6,28

Extraction of bitumen from coal with toluene (I).

5 g of finely ground coal is placed in a Soxhlet apparatus and extracted with freshly distilled toluene for 2 hours until the bitumen compounds are completely extracted. Then the extractant is evaporated and the residue is dried in a vacuum desiccator and weighed, 0.55 g of bitumen compounds are obtained, with a yield of 11.1% of the coal taken before extraction.

Determination of moisture in test coal (II) a). 4 g of coal after extraction of bitumen with toluene is dried in an oven at a temperature of 100-1100C for 2 hours. The charcoal is then kept for 5 minutes at room temperature. Then they are placed in a desiccator over a desiccant and after 20 minutes weighed on an analytical balance. The experiment is repeated 2 more times until a constant weight of coal is obtained, which corresponds to 3.5368 g. The moisture content in it was 0.4632 g (11.59%). b) 4 g of coal is dried at 60-700 above P2O5 to constant weight.

Heating and weighing are repeated four times every 4 hours until a constant weight is reached. Then the experiment is continued in the same way (II). 0.4723 g of coal residue is obtained; after drying it is 3.5212 g (88.19%). The weight of lost moisture is 0.4723g (11.81%).

Determination of ash content of coal (III).

1g of coal is weighed on an analytical balance, placed in a muffle furnace and burned at 600-7000C for 3 hours. Then they take it out of the oven and weigh it on an analytical balance at room temperature and find the mass of ash. To obtain a constant weight, the ash is subjected to repeated firing 2 more times. As a result, 0.1537 g of ash is obtained from 1 g of coal, which is 15.36%.

Isolation of humic acids from brown coal (IV). 2 g of dry coal is placed in a conical flask with a capacity of 0.5 l (flask A), 100 ml of an alkaline solution of sodium pyrophosphate ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$) (11.8 g of $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ + 1 g of NaOH + 250 ml of H_2O) is added and intensively mixed using a mechanical stirrer for 1.5-2 hours, then the contents in the form of a suspension for 15-20 minutes. Centrifuge and decant the aqueous part and transfer it to another flask (flask B). The remaining sediment is washed with 100 ml of 1% NaOH solution and centrifuged. The aqueous part is collected by decanting and poured into flask B, and the sediment is washed again with a 1% NaOH solution. The precipitate is transferred to flask A and the contents are heated for 2 hours in a water bath, then centrifuged.

The aqueous part is decanted into flask B. The remaining precipitate is washed two more times with 100 ml of 10 NaOH solution and centrifuged, the aqueous part is decanted and poured into flask B. The contents in flask B are filtered with a paper filter and transferred to a 1-liter volumetric flask (flask B) and the volume is adjusted to the mark with distilled water. From this volume, take 100 ml of solution into a conical flask and add 60 ml of a 5% HCl solution to it. After some time, humic acids begin to precipitate from the solution. The resulting precipitate is separated by centrifugation.

The aqueous part is decanted, the sediment is washed 2 times with water, and 5 ml of 5% HCl is added to an aliquot for additional precipitation of humic acids. The combined precipitate is filtered through a dry ashless filter and dried in an oven. 0.035 g of humic acids are obtained (the difference in mass during two consecutive weighings was 0.001 g). The weight of humic acid ash after firing this mass into a crucible calcined to a constant weight is 0.0022 g (6.28%).

Using formula (1) determine the mass of coal in the calculation of coal in a dry, ash-free state:

$$m_y = 2 \cdot \frac{100 - (11,59 + 15,36)}{100} = 1,7305$$

Using formula (2), the yield of free humic acids is determined in terms of dry ash-free or dry ash-free and bitumen-free state in percent:

$$m_x = \frac{100 \cdot 1000 (0,037 - 0,0022)}{100 \cdot 1,7305} = 20,34 \%$$

b) From the same volumetric flask (flask B), 100 ml of solution is taken again, 60 ml of 5% HCl is added, then the experiment is carried out under the conditions of example (III). As a result, HA 0.0402 g and ash 0.0012 g (2.98%) are obtained.

c) 100 ml of solution is taken again from the same flask (B), and the experiment is continued under the conditions of example (III). As a result, a HA of 0.0379 g is obtained. The average result of three experiments on the content of humic acids in the tested coal from the Shurob mine is 0.037 g.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that brown and hard coals of Tajikistan are promising sources of humic acids. The extracted humic acids exhibit a complex, polyfunctional structure and contain a wide range of mineral components. The applied extraction methods provide satisfactory yields and reproducible results, making them suitable for further chemical and biological investigations.

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